

Challenges and Strategies in Inclusive Education for Students with Sensory Impairments

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Annotation: This paper explores the specific challenges encountered in teaching English as a foreign language to students with sensory impairments – namely, hearing, vision, and speech difficulties – within inclusive educational settings aims to ensure equitable access to learning for all students, those with sensory disabilities often face barriers that require adapted and specifically designed methodologies. Drawing from academic research and practical strategies, this study sheds light on main obstacles and suggests better approaches to better support English language learners with diverse needs.

Keywords: Inclusive education, English language teaching, sensory impairments, hearing disabilities, visual impairment, speech disorder, special education, EFL.

Аннотация: Данная работа рассматривает специфические трудности, возникающие при обучении английскому как иностранному языку студентов с сенсорными нарушениями – а именно, нарушениями слуха, зрения и речи – в условиях инклюзивного образования. Хотя инклюзивное обучение направлено на обеспечение равного доступа к образованию для всех учащихся, студенты с сенсорными нарушениями часто сталкиваются с уникальными барьерами, требующими адаптированных методик и целенаправленной поддержки. Опираясь на академические исследования и практические стратегии, в данном исследовании обозначаются ключевые препятствия и предлагаются подходы для более эффективной поддержки изучающих английский язык с особыми образовательными потребностями.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное образование, преподавание английского языка, сенсорные нарушения, нарушение слуха, нарушение зрения, речевые расстройства, специальное образование, английский как иностранный (EFL).

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini xorijiy til sifatida o'rgatishda eshitish, ko'rish va nutq bilan bog'liq muammolarga ega bo'lgan o'quvchilarni inklyuziv ta'lim muhitida o'qitish jarayonida uchraydigan muayyan qiyinchiliklar ko'rib chiqiladi. Inklyuziv ta'lim barcha o'quvchilar uchun teng ta'lim olish imkoniyatini ta'minlashni maqsad qilgan bo'lsa-da, sensor buzilishlarga ega o'quvchilar ko'pincha o'ziga xos

"ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIK VA TARJIMASHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI"
mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

to'siqlarga duch kelishadi, bu esa moslashtirilgan uslublar talab qiladi. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar va amaliy strategiyalarga tayangan holda ushbu ilmiy ish asosiy muammolarni ochib beradi va ingliz tilini o'rganayotgan, ehtiyojlari turlicha bo'lgan o'quvchilarni yaxshiroq qo'llab-quvvatlash yo'llarini taklif etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Inklyuziv ta'lim, ingliz tilini o'qitish, sensor buzilishlar, eshitish nuqsoni, ko'rish nuqsoni, nutq buzilishi, maxsus ta'lim, EFL (xorijiy til sifatida ingliz tili).

Inclusion the idea that everyone should be able to use the same facilities, take part in the same activities, and enjoy the same experiences, including people who have a disability or other disadvantage [1].

In recent years, inclusive education, particularly for children with disabilities, has become a prominent subject of discussion both in academic and public spheres. While many individuals to present days propose their own solutions and methodologies, universally accepted approach has been established, and many regions have steadily moved towards implementing inclusive educational practices. However, it's important to acknowledge that a one-size-fits-all solution may never be attainable and some methods need to be adjusted.

Traditionally, special education systems were created to serve children with various disabilities by placing them in separate learning environments. However, life success involves more than just education. In fact, special education often prevents these students from socially integrating. Inclusive education aims to solve this by keeping children with disabilities involved in society throughout their schooling, rather than isolating them. This method not only enhances their communication with the outside world but also improves their chances of successfully adapting to adult life. It's important to note that rigid educational systems frequently exclude children whose individual learning needs cannot be accommodated, making up about 15% of the total student body [2].

Globally, the approach to educating children with disabilities has evolved significantly since the 1960s [3]. Initially, the strategy in the United States was integration—placing children with special needs into mainstream schools when they were considered “ready.” However, this model proved to be limiting, particularly for students with visual or hearing impairments. Increasingly, placing children with developmental disabilities in separate schools is seen as discriminatory. In the U.S., the movement for disability rights has been closely linked with the wider civil rights movement, driven by advocacy from disability organizations and parents of children with disabilities [4]. Students with hearing impairments encounter various challenges in educational settings, such as struggles with speech production, restricted vocabulary growth, and difficulties in understanding lengthy texts. To support these students effectively,

teachers often need to invest extra time and effort to help them fully engage with the learning materials.

To overcome these challenges, educators have implemented various effective teaching strategies. One of the most valuable techniques is visualization, as visual aids greatly improve both vocabulary retention and overall comprehension. Additionally, many teachers utilize the Bilingual-Bicultural Method, which combines sign language and spoken communication, creating a more accessible and inclusive learning environment. [5].

After addressing the issue with the right methods for these types of learners, it is worth mentioning that teachers should be prepared as well. They must exercise patience and willingness to repeat instructions and explanations for several times so that students comprehend what is being taught.

Students with visual difficulties poses different challenges in inclusive classroom, including behavioral concerns, shorter attention spans, and sometimes reduced motivation [6]. Shorter attention spans can be attributed to students' poor vision. It should be noted that even when a healthy person works in a poorly lit room or works with poor quality papers, gradually hers/his concentration will be affected, resulting in not satisfying results.

Educational support for these students often involves **typhlotechnical tools** – such as screen readers, Braille texts, and tactile graphics – as well as the integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) [7]. These tools designed for completely blind or partially blind students to ease their interaction with materials more. Moreover, designing classroom materials in multiple formats (audio, tactile, and digital) ensures inclusivity and improves learner motivation and performance as well as the quality of the lesson.

Teaching English to students with speaking impairments requires specialized methods. These students often face challenges like a limited vocabulary, pronunciation issues, and psychological barriers, including anxiety and low self-esteem. One example of a speech impairment is Spasmodic Dysphonia, a neurological condition that affects voice control, causing involuntary spasms that disrupt speech and make communication difficult [8]. For individuals with this condition, it takes a lot of courage for them to engage in daily conversations, as they experience involuntary spasms that result in voice breaks and difficulty sustaining fluent speech. In an inclusive English language classroom, these learners may struggle with pronunciation, delivering oral presentations, reading aloud, or participating in group discussions.

To better support them, educators can implement multimodal strategies, such as allowing written responses, utilizing speech-to-text technology, and incorporating visual aids in place of verbal communication. Additionally, giving students extra time for speaking exercises aids them significantly in their education journey.

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